

AN ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT CHARACTERISTICS OF PALYNOCYCLES, EUSTATIC CYCLES AND STRATIGRAPHIC SURFACES

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Abstract

The concept of cyclic characterization of palynological records in a sedimentary sequence, referred to here as palynocycles, are connected to eustatic oscillations. Eustatic and climatic cycles are closely associated and are determined by variations in the coastal plant communities which are followed through pollen assemblages. Depositional systems have been found to correspond to phases of sea level oscillations, which in turn correlate with sequences or cycles of fossil pollen assemblages, palynocycles, and are driven by climatic cycles. The ecological communities and assemblages that were important in this concept are ferns, palms, mangroves, open forests and herbs. These formed the bases for relationship involving palynocycles, eustatic cycles and depositional (sequence stratigraphic) systems tracts. This paper presents the stratigraphic behaviours of depositional systems, based on controls of eustacy, subsidence and sediment supply at various scales and phases. Five wells from offshore Niger Delta Basin, Nigeria across the Eastern Thrust/Fold Belt and the Western Thrust Belt, were taken as case study for this work. These wells penetrated a total of seventeen (17) palynocycles presented as PCYL 1 to PCYL 17, dated from 17.7Ma to 0.8Ma and were correlated across the studied wells sections. Some missing intervals or sections and compressed cycles, corresponding to depositional cycles were identified. These may correspond to periods of erosion, forced regression or unfilled incised valleys during or after sediments deposition or stratigraphic condensation episodes, which could have been possible reservoir horizons or potential entrapment systems for hydrocarbon accumulations. This novel relationship approach is developed to advance better understanding of the depositional systems, enhance the development of new stratigraphic plays to search for subtle traps, which may have been bypassed and increase reservoir prospects in the Nigerian basins.

Key words: Palynomorphs; palynocycles; eustacy; palynoflora; palaeoclimate; palaeoecology; bioevents; Miocene.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The concept of cyclic characteristics of palynological records in a sedimentary sequence, being referred to as palynocycle was proposed by Van der Hammen (1957). Poumot (1989), connected palynocycles to eustatic oscillations for Africa and Asia. According to him, eustatic and climatic cycles are associated closely with palynocycles and they are determined by the variations in the coastal plant communities that has been followed through pollen assemblages (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Ecological communities associated with changes in sea-level

Floristic stages which followed one another in inter-tropical Africa are closely linked to climatic changes (Salard-Chebouldaef and Dejax, 1991). (Germeraad et al., 1968; Morley and Richards, 1993) the variations and fluctuations in the distribution of the flora. Various temporal cycles in pollen assemblages have been detected in the northern South America and the cyclic nature of the palynological record was first recognized by Van der Hammen (1957), in Colombia.

The distribution of the pollen and the spores in marine sediments have been found to reflect rather than more accurately the distribution of the vegetation on the adjacent continent (Dupont, 1999; Traverse, 2007; Argant, 2001). Therefore, mainstream of the pollens in the Niger Delta come from the regions north and northeast of the Gulf of Guinea (Figure 1).

The palynological cycles are evidenced by recurrent pollens, like those that correlate with low temperature phases and those that correlate with high temperature phases. According to Van der Hamman (1964), the causes for palynological cycles had been sea level oscillations and temperature produced by variations in the incoming solar radiation.

Palynocycles are of the same nature, even though with different floristic components (because of biogeographical differences), have been recognised in the Paleogene and Neogene of tropical areas from Africa (Van der Zwan and Brugman, 1999). Several of them have been correlated with the 2nd-, 3rd -, and 4th - order global eustatic cycles of Haq et al. (1987).

Eustasy, the world-wide sea-level regime and its fluctuations, caused by absolute changes in the quantity of sea water, e.g. by continental ice-cap fluctuations is measured between the sea- surface and a fixed datum, usually the center of the Earth (Figure 2). It can vary by

changing ocean-basin volume; (e.g. by varying ocean-ridge volume) or by *varying ocean-water volume* (Jervey, 1988).

Figure 2: Definitions of Sea Level (After Kendall, 2006)

Relative sea-level relates to changes in sea level and it depends on both the local and the global controls. The global controls are basically important because they may create allostratigraphic boundaries/units that are globally correlatable (important chronostratigraphic tool) (Warwick et al., 1993). Sea level change exerts an important control on the deposition of sedimentary strata (Figure 3). These units include, Transgressive surfaces of erosion, Regressive surfaces of erosion - ravinement surface, unconformities, - and Maximum flooding surfaces - condensed intervals.

The depositional sequence can be defined as a comparatively conformable sequence of genetically related to the strata bounded by subaerial unconformities or related to their correlative conformities (Haq. et al, 1987). The critical part of this definition is that the sequences are generally bounded above and the below by subaerial unconformities or by correlative conformities (i.e., surfaces that correlate up dip to a subaerial unconformity). Some of the key depositional surfaces include;

Figure 3: Causes and Factors of Sea-Level Change (After Jervey, 1988)

Lowstand Systems Tract (LST): When relative sea-level is at or near the shelf margin and rising slowly, but are slow enough for sedimentation to keep speed with the shelf-edge deltaic process (Posamentier and Vail, 1988). (SPW) the lowstand prograding wedge is characterized by the thick intervals of blocky deltaic sand bodies which are being laterally prograded into by the proximal lagoon shales. Generally shows an initial prograding and aggrading (blocky) parasequence sets depicting a channel fill environment. At the upper boundary of the LST is transgressive surface of erosion (TSE) which marks the first marine incursion landward in the transgressive systems tracts (TST) (Figure 4).

Transgressive Systems Tract (TST): Develops as a result of an increase in the rate of sea-level rise with an overall deepening upward bathymetric signature(Figure 4). This is usually capped with a maximum flooding surface (MFS) at the upper boundary. A prograding parasequence set with upward coarsening signature of a typical shore face environment .

Figure 4: Illustration of a Three - Systems tracts Model

Highstand Systems Tract (HST): During this stage, the sea-level rise decreases and is characterized by initially aggradational deep sea shales that grade into intervals of shallowing upwards. This prograding highstand complex that corresponds to the shoreface of depositional environment. The shoreface sands of the highstand systems tract generally have good reservoir quality in terms of porosity and permeability (Hein, et al; 2014).

This paper presents an overview of the stratigraphic behaviours of depositional systems based on controls of deposition by eustacy, subsidence and sediment supply at various scales and phases from available palynological data obtained from five (5) wells of the offshore Niger Delta Basin in Nigeria. It is aimed at developing a relationship model to advance better understanding of the depositional systems in our basins.

Case Study: Offshore Niger Delta, Nigeria

The study area is located in the offshore Niger Delta, Nigeria, which is situated in the Gulf of Guinea on the West African continental margin. (Figure 5). Wells XE1, XE2 and XE3 are located in the eastern arm of the Charcot fracture zone (Eastern Fold/Thrust belt), while

Wells XW1 and XW2 are located in the western section of the Charcot fracture zone (Western Thrust belt). Generally, the study wells traverse north - west to south - east direction.

Figure 5: Location map showing the study area

The offshore boundary of the province has been defined by the Cameroon volcanic line to its east, and the eastern boundary of the Dahomey basin (the eastern-most West African transform-fault passive margin) to the west, and the two kilometers sediment thickness contour or the 4000-meter bathymetric contour in areas where sediment thickness is greater than two kilometers to the south and southwest (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Map of the Niger Delta Basin Showing the Study Area and Province Outline
(Adapted from Petroconsultants, 1996 and Michele et al. 1999).

The province covers 300,000 km² and includes the geologic extent of the Tertiary Niger Delta Petroleum System. It is ranked among the major prolific deltaic hydrocarbon provinces in the globe and it is the most noteworthy in the West African continental edge. Oil and gas in the Niger Delta are principally produced from sandstones and unconsolidated sand predominantly in the Agbada Formation. yet, turbidite sands which is in the upper Akata Formation is currently the target in deep water offshore and possibly beneath currently producing intervals onshore.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHOD

The materials available for this study include data on five (5) wells (XE1, XE2, XE3, XW1 and XW") from offshore of Niger Delta, fossils distribution charts, maps, Petrel and Stratabugs softwares.

The method adopted for this study involved the review and evaluation of existing biostratigraphic reports and data from the previous publications and wells under review, definition of ecological fossil markers and key stratigraphic used for the study (Evamy et al., 1978), identification of trends of fossils assemblages and distribution within the period, delineation of palynological cycles for each of the well sections based on the distribution of paleo-ecological assemblages or communities in line with sea level fluctuations (Figure 7), reconstruction of palaeo-depositional setting using standard palaeo-bathymetric scheme in line with the global events..

Figure 7: Main Sequence Stratigraphy indication Palynomorphs in the Niger Delta (Modified from Rull and Poumot, 1997).

The theoretical model adopted for this study was used to establish the character of deposition of the systems tracts and the miospores contained in the sediments are calibrated with reference to the models of Posamentier et al. (1988), Morley (1996) Posamentier and Allen (1999), Pross et al. (2001) and Kendell,(2006) and demonstrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Illustration of the relationship between depositional systems, sea level changes and associated palynocycles (Modified from Kendall et al. 2006 by this author).

3.0 RESULTS

The relationship in trends of occurrence of the palynocological groups, in relation to systems tracts in the studied wells, was identified based on the relationship models (Figures 8 and 9). In delineating a palynocycle, each complete cycle is bounded above and below by sequence boundaries (SBs), defined by the return of the fern spores phase (Pross et al., 2001) in the model adopted. This corresponds to model of Vail and Wornardt (1990) and Haq et al. (1987), which assigned sequence boundaries along subaerial unconformities corresponding to successive sea-level lows.

The palynocycle begins with the rise in sea-level, as a peak of palm pollens dominate the incipient prograding sandy deposits and becoming more established. Thereafter, during maximum transgression, an increase of mangrove pollens occur, as the sea-level rises further to more stable condition, giving rise to wetter climates (Hein et al., 2014). The regression phase begins when pollens from back-swamp (back-mangrove) and the open forests begin to flourish under cooler climates, initiating a scenario of competition and dominance with the introduction of the pollen herbs from the hinterland into the incipient environment. Finally, close to the lowest sea-level stand, a phase of dominance by pollens of herbs occurs, indicating a reduction of the mangrove species and its replacement by these other communities (Figure 8). The palynocycle is closed by the return of the fern spores phase (Pross et al., 2001).

The deployment of this novel relationship model (Figure 8) in the interpretation and understanding of the depositional systems of our petroleum basins, helps to show how the relationship between palynocycles, eustatic cycles and key sequence stratigraphic surfaces can be used, to effectively differentiate petroleum systems in adjacent reservoirs, to estimate missing sections in structurally complex areas, build stratigraphic models for exploratory wells with better predictions of target horizons, establish fine scale (high resolution) reservoir correlations and discovery of new reservoirs, as well as, for recalibration of reservoir integrity to enable secondary recovery practices for reserve optimization

The identification of Maximum Flooding Surfaces (MFSs), Condense Sections and Sequence Boundaries (SBs), characterization of systems tract components (highstand - HST, lowstand - LST, transgressive - TST and shelf margin systems tracts - SMST), and deciphering relative sea level changes were identified and calibrated with the Third Order Global Cycle Chart of Haq et al. (1987), with reference to the models of Posamentier et al. (1988), Morley (1996), Posamentier and Allen (1999) and Kendall et al. (2006), as follows.

Figure 9: Relationship between ecological communities, phases of sea level change and depositional cycles

In XE1 well section studied, a total of five candidate Sequence Boundaries (SBs) and five Maximum Flooding Surfaces (MFSs) were identified, which were dated 13.1Ma (3477m), 12.1Ma (3430m), 10.35Ma (3121m), 8.5Ma (2871m) and 6.7Ma (2640m) for SBs and 12.8Ma (3430m), 11.5Ma (3310m), 9.5Ma (2942m), 7.4Ma (2775m) and 6.0Ma (2472m) for MFSs.

The palynocycles interpretation shows that a total of six palynocycles belonging to six depositional cycles of sediments deposition bounded by six sequence boundaries were recognised in the XE1 well section (Figure 10). These are in response to fluctuations in relative sea levels which are largely controlled by climatic conditions and correlate well with the Niger Delta Cenozoic Chronostratigraphic Chart (1988) incorporating the Third Order Cycles Chart of Haq et al.(1987).

Figure 10: Palynocycles interpretation for XE1 well showing the relationship between ecological communities, phases of sea level change and depositional cycles

The analysed interval of XE2 well section witnessed seven candidate SBs and six MFSs proposed as follows; 17.7Ma (4522m), 16.7Ma (4430m), 15.5Ma (4238m), 13.1Ma (3973m), 12.1Ma (3805m), 10.6Ma (3213m) and 8.5Ma (2858m) for SBs and 17.4Ma (4467m), 15.9Ma (4340m), 15.0Ma (4070m), 12.8Ma (3851m), 11.5Ma (3422m) and 9.5Ma (2950m) for the candidate Maximum Flooding Surfaces.

Accordingly, in the XE2 well section interpreted, a total of seven palynocycles belonging to seven depositional cycles of sediments deposition were recognised in the XE2 well section and correlate well with the Niger Delta Cenozoic Chronostratigraphic Chart (1988) incorporating the Third Order Cycles Chart of Haq et al. (1987), as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Palynocycles interpretation for XE2 well showing the relationship between ecological communities, phases of sea level change and depositional cycles.

A total of ten candidate SBs and nine MFSs were proposed for the XE3 well section analysed. These include 17.7Ma (5550m), 16.7Ma (5347m), 15.5Ma (5070m), 13.1Ma (4760m), 12.1Ma (4588m), 10.6Ma (4112m), 10.35Ma (3940m), 8.5Ma (3710m), 6.7Ma (3300m) and 5.6Ma (3160m) for the SBs, while 17.4Ma (5449m), 15.9Ma (5200m), 15.0Ma (4805m), 12.8Ma (4672m), 11.5Ma (4310m), 10.4Ma (3997m), 9.5Ma (3740m), 7.4Ma (3581m) and 6.0Ma (3180m) for MFSs were proposed for the well section.

Here, a total of nine depositional cycles corresponding to the responses of the various ecological communities to climatic conditions as well as the sea level fluctuations during sediment deposition around the study area (Figure 12).

Figure 4.12: Palynocycles interpretation for XE3 well showing the relationship between ecological communities , phases of sea level change and depositional cycles

For the analysed interval of XW1 well section, seven candidate SBs and MFSs each were proposed. These are 17.4Ma (3050m), 11.5Ma (26719m), 10.4Ma (2442m), 9.5Ma (2325m), 7.4Ma (2215m), 6.0Ma (2006m) and 5.0Ma (1813m) were proposed for the MFSs, while 16.7Ma (3018m), 10.6Ma (2708m), 10.35Ma (2408m), 8.5Ma (2271m), 6.7Ma (2086m), 5.6 Ma (1926m) and 4.1Ma (1691m) for Sequence Boundary for the well section.

The study showed that the sediments in XW1 well section analysed recorded seven palynocycles at deposition which correspond to seven cycles of sediment deposition bounded by sequence boundaries, in response to fluctuations in relative sea levels (Figure 13). These also correlate well with the Niger Delta Cenozoic Chronostratigraphic Chart (1988), incorporating the Third Order Cycles Chart of Haq et al. (1987).

Figure 13: Palynocycles interpretation for XW1 well showing the relationship between ecological communities, phases of sea level change and depositional cycles

This section recorded nine palynocycles at deposition according to models of Posamentier et al. (1988), Morley (1996) and Posamentier and Allen (1999), when referenced with the Niger Delta Cenozoic Chronostratigraphic Chart (1988), incorporating the Third Order Cycles Chart of Haq et al. (1987). However, the study shows a thinning upward of the palynocycles relative to those in the lower sections of some of the wells studied (Figure 14). These may not be unconnected with stratigraphic and structural deformations that are typical of the thrust belts in the offshore section of the Niger Delta Basin.

In the XW2 well section seven candidate SBs and six MFSs were proposed. These include 8.5Ma (4387m), 6.7Ma (3850m), 4.1Ma (2663m), 3.7Ma (2260m), 2.4Ma (2060m), 1.6Ma (1720m) and 0.8Ma (1580m) for SBs and 7.4Ma (4200m), 5.0Ma (2973m), 3.9Ma (2381m), 2.7Ma (2120m), 2.0Ma (1900m) and 1.3Ma (1660m).

The sediments in XW2 well section analysed recorded nine palynocycles at deposition. However, the study shows a thinning upward of the palynocycles relative to those in the

lower sections of some of the wells studied (Figure 14). These may not be unconnected with stratigraphic and structural deformations that are typical of the thrust belts of the Niger Delta basin.

Figure 4.14: Palynocycles interpretation for XW2 well showing the relationship between ecological communities, phases of sea level change and depositional cycles.

4.0 DISCUSSIONS

The composite column of all the palynocycles is tagged "general" and is correlated with the Tertiary Global Eustatic Cycles of Haq et al. (1987), shown in Table 1. The general palynocycles identified in the study area penetrated a total of seventeen (17) palynocycles in all and these are represented as PCYL 1 to PCYL 17, and correlated across the studied well sections as follows:

The 'general' Palynocycle, PCYL1 was penetrated only by XE2 and XE3 well sections as palynocycle XE2.1 and XE3.1 and was dated above 17.7Ma (Table 25). This is the oldest depositional cycle recorded throughout the five wells sections studied. Palynocycle PCYL2 was penetrated by XE2, XE3 and XW1 wells and correlated as palynocycles XE2.2, XE3.2 and XW1.1. Palynocycle PCYL3 correlates with only two of the well section as XE2.3 and

XE3.2, while PCYL4 correlates across XE1, XE2 and XE3 wells sections as XE1.1, XE2.4 and XE3.3 respectively.

Table 1: Palynocycles correlation chart demarcated by sequence boundaries

EPOCH	AGE	PALYNOCYCLES CORRELATION						Sequence Boundary	
		XE1WELL	XE2 WELL	XE3 WELL	XW1 WELL	XW2 WELL	GENERAL		
PLIESTOCENE	PLIESTOCENE					XW2.9	PCYL 17	0.8Ma	
						XW2.8	PCYL 16	1.6Ma	
PLIOCENE	LATE					XW2.7	PCYL 15	2.4Ma	
						XW2.6	PCYL 14	3.0Ma	
	EARLY					XW2.5	PCYL 13	3.7Ma	
						XW2.4	PCYL 12	4.1Ma	
MIOCENE	LATE			XE3.9	XW1.7	XW2.3	PCYL 11	5.6Ma	
		XE1.6	XE2.7	XE3.8	XW1.6	XW2.2	PCYL 10	6.7Ma	
		XE1.5	XE2.6	XE3.7	XW1.5	XW2.1	PCYL 9	8.5Ma	
		XE1.4			XW1.4		PCYL 8	10.35Ma	
	MIDDLE		XE1.3			XW1.3		PCYL 7	10.6Ma
			XE1.2	XE2.5	XE3.6	XW1.2		PCYL 6	12.1Ma
				XE3.5			PCYL 5	13.1Ma	
		XE1.1	XE2.4	XE3.4		PCYL 4	15.5Ma		
			XE2.3	XE3.3		PCYL 3	16.7Ma		
		EARLY		XE2.2	XE3.2	XW1.1		PCYL 2	17.7Ma
	XE2.1		XE3.1			PCYL 1			

Cycle PCYL5 and PCYL6, were penetrated by four out of the five well sections studied. It was observed that PCYL5 and PCYL6 were compressed into a somewhat mega palynocycle XW1.2 in XW1 well section, whereas in XE3 well section this was fragmented into XE3.2, XE3.3, XE3.4 and XE3.5. In XE1 and XE2 well sections, PCYL5 and PCYL6 were compressed into XE1.2 and XE2.5 palynocycles respectively. These may be interpreted as discontinuities which may represent minor or major unconformities or hiatuses.

Palynocycles represented as PCYL7, PCYL8 and PCYL9 in the general section were well correlated in XE1, XW1 and XW2, whereas in XE2 and XE3 well sections, these were compacted as XE2.6 and XE3.6 respectively. These may be evidence of compressional nature of thrusting and folding episodes that may have occurred as post depositional features.

PCYL10 is the only palynocycle that was penetrated by all the five well sections studied. Wells XE1, XE2, XE3, XW1 and XW2 penetrated this depositional cycle as XE1.6, XE2.7, XE3.7, XW1.6 and XW2.4 respectively and dated between 6.0Ma to 6.7Ma within the Late Miocene age. Palynocycles PCYL12 and PCYL13 were penetrated by only three wells XE3, XW1 and XW2, being the oldest sediments penetrated by XE3 and XW1 wells, dated between 5.6Ma to 6.0Ma. These represent the interface between Late Miocene and Early Pliocene ages. Palynocycles PCYL12 - PCYL17 were only penetrated by XW2 well section

only as XW2.4 - XW2.9 palynocycles respectively. These have been dated from 4.1Ma to 0.8Ma of Early Pliocene through Late Pliocene to Pliostocene age as the youngest sediments deposited within the study area.

This correlation made it possible to identify some missing intervals or sections, corresponding to depositional cycles as observed among the three well sections in the Eastern Thrust/Fold Belts and between the two well sections in the Western Thrust Belt. In general, this phenomenon is also identified when correlating across the two thrust belts, particularly, in the XE2 and XE3 (Eastern Thrust/Fold Belt) and XW1 (Western Thrust Belt). Cycles XE2.5, XE3.4, XE3.4 and XE3.5 in the Eastern Thrust Belt (XE2 and XE3 wells) are compressed into only one Cycle (Cycle XW1.2) in the Western Thrust Belt (XW1 well).

The compressed cycles within the analysed well sections and across the two thrust belts may be regarded as stratigraphic condensation episodes. These evidences may correspond to periods of erosion, forced regression or unfilled incised valleys during or after sediments deposition (Posamentier et al., 1988). Also, the study shows that it is cumbersome to correlate across large distances in the sections perpendicular to the coast and in the deep offshore settings, because of the preponderance or the intensity of faulting. However, the missing depositional sequences could have been possible reservoir horizons or potential entrapment systems for hydrocarbon accumulations.

Consequently, the integration of sequence stratigraphic interpretations with the distribution or changes in ecological composition within a depositional cycle makes clearer, possible existence of minor and major hiatuses in the analysed sections as demonstrated in Figure 11. A correlation across the ETB and WTB section shows that the youngest sediments penetrated were identified in the WTB and was dated by 0.8Ma SB, while the oldest sediments dated by 17.7Ma MFS were identified in wells sections within the ETB (Table 1).

5.0 CONCLUSIONS

The concept of cyclic characteristics in the palynological record are directly related to climatic cycles which are driven by the effects of eustatic events on coastal ecosystems. The sequential records of fossil pollens assemblages can be calibrated with sea level oscillations and their phases and linked to particular depositional systems tracts.

These demonstrations show a great fit between palynocycles and the global eustatic cycles of Haq et al., (1987) for the Neogene sediments of the Niger Delta.

The application of the palynocycles concept, an aspect of high resolution correlation design, will contribute to the improvement of exploration practices in the Nigerian basins, in that it defines more precisely the stratigraphic and exploratory intervals of interest and makes it easily detectable in both seismic and electric logs. Furthermore, its application as a palynostratigraphic tool in stratigraphic resolution has substantially improved the

identification of events reflecting climatic, tectonic, orographic and sea level changes that have contributed to the configuration of petroleum systems within the Niger Delta basin.

This novel relationship approach can be used to build stratigraphical models for exploratory and production wells with better predictions of target horizons at reservoir scales by integrating all interpreted data to reconstruct the stratigraphic architecture, capable of predicting depositional systems as it relates to petroleum exploration and exploitation in Nigeria.

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